

FORENSIC EVALUATION OF DIFFUSE AXONAL INJURY

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Relevance. Traumatic brain injury is damage to the skull and brain by various mechanical agents during trauma. Sudden damage to the brain in emergency situations leads to irreversible processes. Diffuse axonal injury is a type of traumatic brain injury that occurs as a result of a closed brain injury, with damage to the bones of the skull. Traumatic brain injury is one of the leading causes of death and disability worldwide.

Goal. Diffuse damage to axons leads to axonal degeneration, causing a greater reduction in anisotropy. Primary brain damage, in particular diffuse axonal damage, is a trigger mechanism for degenerative changes in axons and myelin sheaths of the white matter of the brain, leading to their destruction and atrophy. Evaluation allows you to identify ways to prevent further complications of the brain.

Problem. Diffuse axonal injury of the brain is diffuse damage to the axons of the nervous system and affects the white matter tracts. Characterized by a prolonged coma of patients from the moment of injury. In this case, the following symptoms are expressed: paresis of the reflex upward gaze, divergence of the eyes along the axis, bilateral inhibition of the pupillary reaction to light. Vegetative disorders are expressed: arterial hypertension, high temperature, hyperhidrosis, increased salivation. Along the way, signs of secondary degeneration of the white matter along the conduction pathways of the central nervous system near the site of nerve rupture were revealed. In places of primary axon ruptures, a moderate macrophage reaction with the formation of granular globules was determined. With the injury, there was a decrease, and by the end of the first month, the complete disappearance of axonal glomeruli along the damaged nerve.

Conclusion. With the advent of positron emission tomography in clinical practice, in vivo diagnosis of primary axonotomy became possible not only in diffuse axonal injury, but also in other forms of TBI, the genesis of which is associated with inertial displacement of the brain in the cranial cavity. The main histological comparisons are methods that allow to detect changes in axial cylinders - silver impregnation according to Bilshovsky, myelin sheaths -

osmium impregnation according to Marx to detect early demyelination, Spielmeier stain to detect late demyelination. The information obtained fully helps to make a diagnosis in the forensic medical evaluation of this states.

